

The Role of Satisfaction on Performance among Afe Babalola University Team Sports

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Abstract—Viability and competency during competition is the dream of every team sports so as to have a good result. But it seems factors abound which deter the performance of even a good sports team. Different individuals with different state of mind all come together to perform in team sports with different degree of satisfaction. This study investigated the role of satisfaction on performance among Afe Babalola University team sports. Descriptive survey research design was used and the population consists of all male and female athletes in the team sports that participated in the last 2019 Ekiti State Higher Institution games (ESHIGA). Total enumeration technique was used for the three team sports; football (44), basketball (24) and volleyball (24). A total of 92 participants were involved in the research. The instrument used for the study was a modified Athlete Satisfaction Scale (ASS). The questionnaire was divided into two sections. The Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient of 0.71 was obtained. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 significant levels. The completed questionnaire was collated, coded, and analyzed using descriptive statistics of frequency counts and percentage and inferential statistics of chi-square (X^2). Findings of this study revealed that satisfaction significantly influences team sports performance among Athletes of Afe Babalola University. The responsibility of satisfying athlete lies on the coaches, fans, sports administrators as well as organizers of such event, as it is not only financial reward that gives satisfaction. The performance of a team sports is quiet important and its being determined by the degree of satisfaction of each individual that make up the team. All effort must be made to satisfy athlete in order to guarantee optimum performance.

Keywords—Athlete satisfaction, Optimum achievement, Optimum performance, Sports performance and Team sports.

I. INTRODUCTION

TEAM sports competition is usually a lively event as a group of individual comes together to achieve the same goal. Every team member is important and their individual role is significant in striving to win a game or the competition as a whole. Teams are defined as formal and organized groups of individuals who work interdependently, have common goals, and are mutually accountable for task accomplishment and meet regularly to accomplish the team's goals [2]. The team's goals and expectations provide a target for team performance, but to achieve those targets, team members need to develop a shared understanding of how best to coordinate their actions and work together to accomplish team goals. Attitudes and behaviors of team members and their concern for others are linked to team performance [3].

Every team pass through series of transition and in the

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process there is always the need to have an adequate organization structure and environmental management in order to achieve the overall goal of the team. This requires every member of the team playing their role as expected with little monitoring. Teams that have clear roles and mutual expectations provide a stable internal coordination for the team which leads to improved team performance [4]. Team sports like football, basketball and volleyball are pride of sports in Afe Babalola University. At the beginning of each session each team sports provide an avenue for recruitment of new players with hundreds of students trying their best to make the team. There are average of two completions held every semester not counting the states and National events. In the just concluded Ekiti Sate Higher Institutions Games (ESHIGA) hosted by Afe Babalola University from March 4 to March 7, 2019, Afe Babalola University came first with all the team sports playing in the finals.

TABLE I
ESHIGA FINAL MEDAL TABLE

Name of Institution	GLD	SIL	BRZ
Afe Babalola University	22	14	15
Federal Poly Ado Ekiti	11	6	3
Ekiti State University	10	13	9
Federal University Oye	5	5	10
SCH. of Nursing Ekiti	1	6	8
Fabotas College	1	0	7
College of edu. Ikere	0	1	8
COLL. of HLTH. SCI. & TECH	0	3	0

Athletes' satisfaction always reflects in their performance especially in team games where a group of athletes come together with only one single goal. Every teammate is a key to the overall success but all depend on their performance, practices, coaching, facilities etc. In Afe Babalola University all members of the sports school team maintain cordial relationship with each other. The University community appreciates sports as there are no sports without coaches or facilities. Satisfaction in sports is even more important than actual athletic success [5]. Athlete satisfaction is very vital as it brings in positive attitude towards training and competitions. Satisfaction also depends on what the athlete wants, as there may be variation in terms of needs and this can be noticed even during performance at training and match days.

Satisfaction is a psychological state that is attainable in sports, its role is very vital especially in terms of performance and enjoyment. Satisfaction is an integral part of sports participation and enjoyment [5]. It is a positive, affective state derived from evaluation of structures, processes, and outcomes

associated with the athletic experience. It can improve athletes' performance and the degree to which he achieves his expected goal. Athlete satisfaction is accepted as a crucial building block of affective success and efficiency [6]. Athletes' satisfaction is regarded as the essence of life or the physical effort made by the management in the organization as perceived by the athlete. It is a progressive change made as a result of compound evaluation of arrangement, processes, and outcome associated with the athlete's experience. Satisfaction sometimes is different from the perception of what the athletes received as a prize and what they really want [7].

In 2019 ESHIGA games, Afe Babalola University team sports excel in the competition. A lot of variables may have led to this but satisfaction tends to be one of such variables. Several variables have been studied together with satisfaction in sport although leadership seems to be most researched one [1], [8], [9]. Also sport psychologists now study athlete satisfaction as part of antecedent or outcome variable. Also researches on performance in sports have generally focused on stress control [10], attention [11], self-esteem [12], motivation [13], [14] and team cohesion [15], [16]. This research work investigated the role of satisfaction on performance among Afe Babalola University team sports.

Hypothesis

Satisfaction will not significantly influence team performance among Athletes of Afe Babalola University team sports.

II. METHODOLOGY

The design of the study was the descriptive survey research. The population consists of all male and female athletes in the team sports that participated in the last ESHIGA games. Total enumeration technique was used for the three team sports; football male and female team (44); basketball male and female team (24) and volleyball male and female team (24). A total of 92 participants were involved in the research.

TABLE II
DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BY SPORTS

Sports Team	Male	Female	Total
Football	22	22	44
Basketball	12	12	24
Volleyball	12	12	24
Sum total			92

Instrument

The instrument used for the study was ASS. The instrument was modified from a multiple-item, multi-dimensional scale developed by [1]. It was developed in 1998 to derive athlete satisfaction. The instrument consists of two sections. Section A seeks information on demographic data of the respondents, while section B was used to elicit information on athlete satisfaction on performance. The modified instrument which consists of 15 items has a reliability coefficient of 0.71.

Procedure

The instrument was administered to all the sports teams

after a meeting with the management of the Institution a week after the ESHIGA games. The coaches were effectively used as research assistant. The data were collected immediately after the meeting.

Data Analysis

The completed copies of the questionnaire were collated, coded and analyzed, using descriptive and inferential statistics. Frequency counts and percentages were used for the demographic characteristics of the respondents while inferential statistics of chi-square (X^2) was used to test the stated hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Out of the 92 administered instruments, 85 were analyzed.

III. PRESENTATION OF RESULT

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

TABLE III
DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BY GENDER

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	43	50.59
Female	42	49.41
Total	85	100.0

The findings of the study as indicated in Table III showed that male respondents accounted for 50.59% of the sample with a frequency of 43 while their female counterparts accounted for 49.41% with a frequency of 42 respondents. This is as a result of the fact that the University is not gender biased as both male and female team gets equal attention with the administration of the University.

TABLE IV
DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BY AGE

Age Range	Frequency	Percent
17 -20 Years	47	55.29
21 - 24 Years	32	37.65
25 and above	6	7.06
Total	85	100.0

The findings of the study as shown in Table IV revealed that respondents within 17-20 years with a frequency of 47 respondents accounted for the largest proportion of the respondents with a percentage contribution of 55.29%, while 37.65% of the respondents are within 21-24 years with a frequency of 32. The remaining 7.06% were accounted for respondents that are 25 and above with a frequency of 6, which happens to be the least represented respondents. Most of the students in the University graduate before the age of 24 years as there are no strike action or any form of delay that could elongate the graduation of the students.

The findings of the study as shown in Table V revealed that 22 of the respondents were from the college of social and management sciences which accounted for the largest proportion of the respondents with a percentage contribution of 25.88%, while the college of law has the least respondents with a frequency of 13 and percentage contribution of 15.29%. All the colleges in the University participate actively in sports, the school time table provide the period of 3:00pm – 7:00pm

as break every day for sports and other social activities.

TABLE V
DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BY COLLEGE

College	Frequency	Percent
Engineering	20	23.53
Law	13	15.29
MHS	11	12.94
Sciences	19	22.35
SMS	22	25.88
Total	85	100.0

TABLE VI
DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BY LEVEL

Level	Frequency	Percent
100	13	15.29
200	18	21.18
300	27	31.77
400	15	17.65
500	12	14.12
Total	85	100.0

The findings of the study as shown in Table VI revealed that respondents in 300 level accounted for a frequency of 27 which happens to be the largest proportion of the respondents and a percentage contribution of 31.77%, while the least respondents are from 500 level with a percentage contribution of 14.12% and a frequency contribution of 12. The competitive nature of each team makes it difficult for new students to make it easily except the dedicated ones. With perseverance and commitment, they are able to cope with the training and other challenges involved.

Hypothesis

Satisfaction will not significantly influence performance among Athletes of Afe Babalola University team sports.

TABLE VII
INFLUENCE OF ATHLETE SATISFACTION CHI-SQUARE RESULT

Response	Freq	%	X ² (Cal)	X ² (Tab)	df	Rmk
Strongly Agree	523	41.01	32.05	23.69	14	Sig
Agree	364	28.55				
Strongly Disagree	99	7.77				
Disagree	289	22.66				

Table VII shows that X²calculated value of 32.05 is greater than the table value of 23.05 at df of 14, at 0.05 level of significance. Since the X² calculated value is greater than the table value, the hypothesis is thereby rejected thus showing a significant athlete satisfaction influence on team sports performance. This therefore leads to the conclusion that satisfaction significantly influences team sports performance among Athletes of Afe Babalola University.

III. DISCUSSIONS

This study examined the role of satisfaction on performance among Afe Babalola University team sports. The finding of the hypothesis as shown in Table VII indicated that satisfaction significantly influences team sports performance among Athletes of Afe Babalola University. This result corroborates the findings of [17]; he reported three motives

behind athlete satisfaction. First, there is a connection between athlete's satisfactions and his or her performance in a given sports. For example, an athlete who is more satisfied will put out more effort and persistence during competition. The second reason that athlete satisfaction is important is because satisfaction can be seen as a precursor or outcome in the conceptual frameworks of other constructs, such as cohesion. The final reason is that athletic satisfaction is a key concern in athletic programs. Athlete's satisfaction determines basically achievement of goals and approval of social agents' such as coach, parents and teammates [18].

Reference [19] also reported that in evaluating high performance teams, we must identify two ways of thinking about effectiveness. Firstly, the internal factors or conditions include the part played by the coaches to ensure skill acquisition and productivity on the team. Secondly, the external factors include the available facilities, communication network, the institutional structure, remuneration and other fringe benefits.

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Athlete satisfaction was discovered to have contributed to the team sports performance of Afe Babalola University athlete that participated in the last ESHIGA games in 2019. The degree of satisfaction is usually expressed in team sports through performance. Athlete satisfaction goes beyond financial reward as each individual has a different set goal which must be considered in order to achieve the set goal of the team in general. Athlete satisfaction is an important tool for optimum performance during competition. Satisfied athlete is likely to put in more effort towards participation. For optimum achievement in sports satisfaction it is an important variable to be considered. Without satisfaction it is impossible to have optimum performance, it will hinder the desired success. Athlete satisfaction must be put into consideration in any level of sports organization for optimum achievement. Sports organizers and stakeholders in sports have a role to play by ensuring satisfaction of their athlete before, during and after competition.

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